

MECHANICAL TESTING OF 3D-PRINTED HIGH-PERFORMANCE-THERMOPLASTICS FOR CRYOGENIC APPLICATIONS: EVALUATION OF PROCESSING PARAMETERS AND TEST SET-UP

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ABSTRACT

In recent years, socioeconomic trends drive research aimed at establishing hydrogen as a clean energy source. Especially the decarbonization of travel presents itself as a vital aspect of this development. However, integrating hydrogen into weight sensitive applications such as aircraft presents unique challenges including proposed weight gains and limited storage space, with liquid hydrogen taking up several times more volume than kerosene. These challenges may be resolved through utilization of modern manufacturing techniques, including additive manufacturing and use of high-performance materials. Selecting materials able to withstand the harsh hydrogen environment and extreme cold temperatures associated with its liquid storage is critical. In general, materials tend to embrittle as the temperature drops. Furthermore, many traditional metals suffer from additional hydrogen-embrittlement, making them unsuitable for hydrogen infrastructure. In contrast, high-performance thermoplastics offer resilient alternatives to hydrogen and exhibit promising mechanical behavior at low temperatures. However, testing mechanical behavior of additively manufactured samples at cryogenic temperatures requires a non-standardized setup and often yields unreliable data. Furthermore, the printing process heavily influences material properties. This paper aims to evaluate a selection of parameters focusing on interlayer bonding to provide more reliable fracture data and proposes a setup for the evaluation of cryogenic material behavior.

1. INTRODUCTION

As global awareness of climate change and environmental protection continues to grow, the European Commission proposed an ambitious hydrogen strategy in July 2020 aimed at accelerating the development of clean hydrogen. This strategy forms an essential part of the plan for a climate-neutral Europe by 2050 and aims to establish hydrogen as a mainstay of the future energy system. These actions also affect the aviation industry, incentivizing research in hydrogen-based propulsion systems. However, hydrogen, especially in its liquid form, presents specific challenges that entail special material requirements. These can potentially be met using so-called semi-crystalline high-performance thermoplastics, which appear suitable for applications in the storage and transport of liquid hydrogen due to their properties.

The processing of these plastics to produce the necessary components reveals manufacturing restrictions and interactions between the material and process that have a significant impact on the mechanical properties of the end products. This is particularly true for additive manufacturing processes such as fused filament fabrication (FFF), where the anisotropy of the

materials, especially the weak bonding in the upright build direction, poses a significant challenge. The design of the specimen and the way in which the specimens are printed - whether individually or in a group, upright or cut out of an overall specimen, as well as the printing strategy - has a significant influence on the mechanical properties of the specimens. This can influence crystal growth, both along the printing direction and across the layer structure and change the resulting characteristic values. In view of this complexity, it is crucial to develop adapted test methods and standards for comparison that enable a reliable evaluation of the material properties, considering the weakest orientation along the vertical axis.

This article compares material parameters extracted from the literature and analyzed in terms of their variance, supplemented by own empirical data on various manufacturing parameters. The effect of these processing parameters on the interlayer bonding and resulting tensile strength is analyzed in detail. Following the analysis of these results, the paper argues on the application and transferability of the findings to cryogenic test conditions. To this end, an adapted test-setup for performing cryogenic tests is presented. The aim is to develop a deeper understanding of the relationship between the printing process and resulting material behavior, and to improve the reliability and reproducibility of test results.

2. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Safely utilizing additively manufactured components in engineering applications requires knowledge of their mechanical behavior. This is especially true for demanding applications such as under severe environmental conditions, as is the case for use at cryogenic temperatures. Exposure of polymers to these temperatures, typically falling within the range below $-150\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, among other effects results in an increase in tensile strength and stiffness alongside a significant reduction in ductility [1]. To date, there exist only a few published studies investigating these behavioral trends for FFF processed polymers. Cruz et al. [2] investigated the tensile strength of different polyamides in XY (in plane) and Z (out of plane) direction for FFF and powder bed fusion (PBF) 3D printed samples at 77K. Weiss et al. [3] compares thermal and mechanical properties of a photocuring polymers processed via PolyJet™ modelling and FFF printed ABS samples at 77K and 4.2K respectively, but does not clearly specify printing direction of the tested samples. Bartolome et al. [4] also reports on in plane tensile behavior of FFF printed ABS samples for laboratory equipment in biomedical applications at 77K while Saenz et al. [5] investigates tensile strength of FFF printed ABS samples with variation in layer height, infill pattern and infill density. Vaught et al. [6] expands the evaluation of in plane cryogenic tensile strength at 77K to several other commodity polymers including ABS, PETG as well as filled and non-filled PLA. Finally, Kartikeyan et al. [7] compares thermal and tensile properties of traditionally extruded and machined samples made from the high performance thermoplastic PEEK with FFF printed samples at room temperature and at 77K. Table 1 shows the recorded tensile strength for FFF-printed samples at 77K across all mentioned studies and compares them to recorded strength values at room temperature where available.

Table 1: Comparison of cryogenic tensile strength across reviewed literature

Source	Material	Temperature [K]	Tensile Strength [MPa]	
			In plane (XY)	Out of plane (Z)
Cruz et al.	PA12	77K	45.8	30.6
		Ambient	46	38.5
Weiss et al.	ABS	77K	32	N/A
		Ambient	35	N/A
Bartolome et al.	ABS (as printed)	77K	4.2	N/A
		Ambient	N/A	N/A
	ABS (annealed)	77K	16.1	N/A
		Ambient	N/A	N/A
Saenz et al.	ABS	77K	29.42	N/A
		Ambient	36.25	N/A
Vaught et al.	ABS	77K	57.3	N/A
		Ambient	37.7	N/A
	PETG	77K	117.6	N/A
		Ambient	45.6	N/A
	PLA	77K	122	N/A
		Ambient	47.2	N/A
	PLA-CF	77K	132	N/A
		Ambient	37.4	N/A
Kartikeyan et al.	PEEK	77K	109	N/A
		Ambient	99	N/A

While reviewing the listed data, it becomes apparent that there are significant deviations in the reported material behavior, even for samples made from the same polymer type and tested under similar conditions. As such, the reported tensile strength of tested ABS samples ranges from 4.2 MPa up to 57.3 MPa. This gap makes it difficult to utilize these values for engineering tasks, as fracture behavior seems to be unreliable. Furthermore, contrary to the anticipated effects of cryogenic testing temperature on the polymer’s strength, most FFF 3D-printed samples remain stagnant or become weaker across all reviewed studies. A notable exemption from this trend are the samples tested by Vaught et al. [6] who was able to ensure more reliable fracturing and showed to be expected strength gains in samples tested at 77K through use of a customized sample geometry. While the adaptation of customized samples proved successful in producing more reliable fracture data, a design adaptation alone does not justify the significant deviations in recorded tensile strength and the lack of strength gains across most tested samples. However, a possible explanation for the observed premature fracture is indicated by Bartolome [4] and Cruz [2] by weak interlayer bonding within the printed samples. The bonding process across printed layers may be described by autohesion with the driving mechanisms being diffusion and entanglement of polymer chains across the interface at temperatures above the glass transition and in the case of semi crystalline thermoplastics interfacial crystalline growth [8]. To gain insight into the bonding process during manufacturing and its effect on the mechanical properties, this paper investigates the printing process for samples made from the high-performance thermoplastic PEEK while focusing on

manufacturing parameters affecting interlayer bonding. As the initial interlayer bonding strength represents a process induced characteristic not tied to environmental testing conditions, all testing is performed at ambient temperature. Secondly, conclusions from the ambient testing are drawn and incorporated into a cryogenic testing set-up for future evaluation of material behavior under cryogenic conditions.

3. EXPERIMENTATION

As mentioned earlier, interlayer bonding of semi-crystalline thermoplastics as described by autohesion is mainly driven by the three phenomena interdiffusion, entanglement and interfacial crystalline growth. All these phenomena are predominantly favored by high temperatures above the glass transition and slow cooling rates. As such, printing parameters directly affecting the interface temperature as well as the cooling process were selected as nozzle temperature, chamber temperature, print speed and fan setting and studied through a two-level full factorial design of experiments (DOE). An ordinary least squares linear regression was performed with the Minitab® software to develop a regression model converging with the response values at a confidence level of 95 %. The model was used for a parameter optimization aimed at maximizing the interlayer bonding strength. Implementing a simulation based approach for the assessment of the interlayer bonding strength through simulation of the thermal history during printing as described by Driezen et al. [9], the variation of factors according to the DOE testing matrix was performed in a virtual environment. The factors as well as their chosen levels are shown in Table 2. The levels are derived based upon previously developed parameters as well as limits given by the material supplier data sheet, with the intention to cover a broad range to allow for significant change in the response value over the level range. Lastly, a direct comparison of pre – and post optimized parameters was performed through mechanical tensile testing of eight samples each [8, 10, 11].

Table 2: Factors and corresponding levels for the two-level full factorial design

Factor	Low Level	High Level
A: Nozzle temperature	370 °C	440 °C
B: Chamber temperature	190 °C	235 °C
C: Print speed	30 mm/s	60 mm/s
D: Fan speed	10 %	100 %

In lack of published standards adequately representing tensile testing of additively manufactured polymer samples, researchers commonly refer to ASTM D638 and ISO 572 intended for testing of unreinforced and reinforced plastics usually manufactured through extrusion, or (injection) molding processes [12, 13]. Following this procedure, the bonding strength at the interface between neighboring layers is evaluated through standardized tensile tests in accordance with ISO 572-2, utilizing sample geometry type BA at a testing speed of 5mm/min. All tests are performed on upwards oriented samples printed perpendicular to the print platform (Z-direction) such that loading during testing is applied perpendicular to the created layer interface as shown in Figure 1 [14].

Figure 1: Tensile testing of interlayer bonding strength through perpendicular loading to layer interface. Adapted from [15].

In an effort to exclude the influence of infill angles, all samples are made up of parallel oriented wall lines only. Printing of individual tensile specimens along the Z axis imposes challenges through their slender and elongated geometry, frequently resulting in geometrical deviations impairing the sample integrity. To circumnavigate this issue, a similar printing strategy as described by Moetazedian et al. [15] is adapted. Instead of printing individual tensile samples, specimens are cut out from a printed tower instead. Cutting operations were performed in a similar manner for all specimens, using a circular diamond saw without additional cooling, as this resulted in the most accurate cuts. Specimens cut from the tower mimic the shape and cross-sectional area of the referenced ISO 572-2 type BA specimen through variation in thickness along the Z-axis, as shown in Figure 2. Cutting samples from this tower ensures the production and testing of samples with higher consistency and better geometrical accuracy than would result from directly printing specimens along the Z-axis. The filament used in this study was Luvocom® 3F PEEK 9581.

Figure 2: Model of the printed tower (left). Tensile specimen cut out from the tower, clamped inside the tensile testing machine (right)

4. RESULTS

The developed regression model converges well with the simulation data, indicated through an R^2 value of 98.04 %. Figure 3 shows a pareto chart of the standardized effects of studied factors on the response value for the developed interlayer strength regression model. The pareto chart highlights the statistically significant influence of all studied main factors, as well as three second order interactions, through the visual expansion of the individual bars beyond the red significance line. While all factors seem to exert a significant influence on the response value, the chamber temperature appears to be by far the most important one.

Pareto Chart of the Standardized Effects

(response is Y2 (Tensile strength); $\alpha = 0,05$)

Figure 3: Pareto chart of the standardized effects for the developed interlayer tensile strength model

A further analysis of the influence of the statistically significant factors given through the corresponding effect plot in Figure 4 shows increasements in tensile strength to be expected with increasing settings of nozzle temperature, chamber temperature and printing speed and lower settings of the fan. Statistically significant interactions between these factors, as shown in Figure 5, proof to be reinforcing each other at higher temperature settings and generally follow the same trends as the main factors themselves.

Figure 4: Main effect plot for the developed interlayer tensile strength model

Figure 5: Interaction plot for the developed interlayer tensile strength model

The performed analysis appears to provide coherent results through favoring higher process temperatures and lower forced cooling through the fan, both conditions beneficial to autohesion. An optimization of factors over the observed level range results in values set at the upper level. The coincidence of the factor optimums with the selected upper boundary indicates a true optimum outside the observed level range. Since the chosen 2-level design limits the analysis to the design space, additional experiments should be performed in future work to identify this true optimum. Nevertheless, the so far performed optimization was validated through tensile testing. Table 3, shows the pre- and post-optimization parameter sets used for this validation.

Table 3: Pre- and post-optimization parameter sets

Factor / Parameter	Pre-Optimization	Post-Optimization
Nozzle temperature	425 °C	440 °C
Chamber temperature	200 °C	235 °C
Print speed	50 mm/s	60 mm/s
Fan setting	100 %	10 %

The recorded tensile data for both parameter sets is given in Figure 6. During testing, many samples fractured close to the grips, in the transition between the gauge length and gripping area. All tested samples show brittle fracture behavior, with an average tensile strength of 18.4 MPa pre-optimization and a large increase in average tensile strength to 56.3 MPa along additional gains in fracture strain post-optimization. As such, the average tensile strength post-optimization correlates to roughly 60% of the tensile strength reported for injection molded samples in the material data sheet [11].

Figure 6: Tensile test results pre- and post-optimization

The increase in average tensile strength of around 206% achieved through optimization of printing parameters alone highlights the significance of manufacturing conditions in FFF printing. It is noteworthy that most of the previously reviewed literature fails to report on the details of sample manufacturing, especially on the basic printing settings studied in this report.

In face of the enormous variation in achievable tensile strength at ambient testing temperature tied to autohesion promoting parameter settings, this may give a plausible indication for the vast discrepancy in the reported cryogenic material properties and the observed lack of tensile strengthening across the reviewed literature. Future experiments at cryogenic testing temperature will show if this hypothesis proves to be valid.

4.1 Adaption of test-setup for cryogenic tensile testing

Testing at ambient temperature reveals a significant influence of processing parameters on the achievable tensile strength. The testing setup however repeatedly provoked failure outside the narrow-gauge length, close to or in the transition to the wider gripping area. This leads to an underestimation of the actual material strength. A potential cause for this phenomenon may be the presence of structural defects within the specimens prior to loading. However, a similar behavior seems to be widely reported for testing of unidirectional composites and is attributed to the relatively high transversal clamping pressure as well as potential sample damage introduced through serrated grip surfaces leading to unfavorable loading, stress concentrations at the grips and ultimately premature failure close to the gauge length [16].

Cryogenic testing temperatures may further add to this unfavorable stress state where temperature induced thermal stresses as well as loss of ductility may further promote premature failure in the gripping area as observed by Siddiqui et al. [17] and Vaught et al. [6]. Adapting these considerations, future cryogenic tests will be performed with fully submerged specimens and form-fit gripping as shown in Figure 7, in an attempt to prevent stress concentrations and damage due to transversal clamping, promoting more reliable fracture data.

Figure 7: Proposed test-setup (left) with form fit gripping for cryogenic tensile testing (right)

5. CONCLUSIONS

Available cryogenic mechanical data of FFF printed thermoplastics shows widely inconsistent behavior, likely caused by weak bonding resulting in premature material failure. Most of the reviewed studies do not give information on essential printing parameters. However, nozzle temperature, chamber temperature, print speed and fan setting all have been shown to significantly influence the interlayer bonding in FFF printing. Optimizing these printing parameters to promote the interlayer bonding process successfully increased the tensile strength of FFF printed PEEK in Z-direction by 206% and clearly highlighted the importance of printing conditions for a reliable mechanical evaluation of additively processed thermoplastics. Therefore, publications should include details on printing parameters and sample manufacturing to make the derived mechanical data comprehensible and comparable. Additionally, this significant strength increase mitigates inferior out of plane behavior commonly associated with FFF printed components, making them a more viable solution for demanding engineering applications. Finally, considerations from ambient testing have been drawn and processed into a new test-setup for future cryogenic tensile testing. This new test-setup as well as the evident relationship between printing parameters and interlayer bonding will be verified for its usefulness in providing more reliable cryogenic fracture data in upcoming experiments. A successful adaptation to cryogenic testing temperatures, will play a vital role for the development of liquid hydrogen infrastructure, especially for use in aircraft, as the incorporation of additively processed high strength thermoplastics may aid in the manufacturing of lightweight components.

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